

SSH Training Discovery Toolkit

A lack of quick availability of relevant training materials often limits Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) trainers in developing training activities and programmes. The SSH Training Discovery Toolkit addresses this gap by improving the discoverability and providing access to effective and often ready-to-use training resources. In the long run, we hope the tool will make providing training on Open Science, Research Data Management, FAIR and open data easier to all European SSH communities, thus supporting the shift of the current research culture towards Open Science.

What is a SSH Training Discovery Toolkit?

The SSH Training Discovery Toolkit ("Toolkit" in short) is an inventory of various learning and training materials that trainers of different disciplines in the SSH can use to find materials for re-use in their own training activities. The Toolkit links to a variety of materials available through various sources on topics including Open Science, Research Data Management, and didactics, but also specific topics that are relevant to multiple disciplines, like text encoding and spatial data. The Toolkit is continuously being updated and currently contains more than 180 items from 78 different sources on the above-mentioned topics for better development and implementation of training activities.

Key features

While it primarily targets trainers, the Toolkit also contains links to training materials targeting other audiences available for the SSH communities. The Toolkit is designed in close collaboration with the [SSH Training Community](#) to make available training resources discoverable and encourage re-use and exchange.

The Toolkit offers a systematic collection of available materials which are described using metadata and a set of controlled vocabularies that can be used to filter and structure the information.

Benefits

- ➔ The Toolkit helps to make the process of training preparation and delivery more efficient and effective.
- ➔ The Toolkit is curated, which means it is continuously improved in its content and functionality, based on the feedback from trainers (users) and the SSH Training Community.

- ➔ The Toolkit is also being updated taking into consideration the work and recommendations of other international initiatives including the EOSC working group on skills and training, as well as the RDA IG Education and Training on handling of Research Data (ETHRD) and the EOSC Future project.
- ➔ The collected metadata for the various training resources will be aligned with metadata models developed within the EOSC and dedicated Research Data Sharing (RDA) groups to ensure that the information in the Toolkit is interoperable and can be integrated into other services.

Training and Support

More Information

- ➔ [D6.7 Inventory of existing learning materials](#)
- ➔ [D6.9 SSHOC Trainer Toolkit \(draft\)](#)
- ➔ [MS39 Launch expertise strategy](#)
- ➔ [MS40 SSHOC Training Toolkit \(preliminary version\)](#)
- ➔ [Training Discovery Toolkit Poster](#)

Who made the tool

All partners involved in WP6, task 6.4: Building Expertise: theSSHOC Training Network (Lead: KNAW(DANS), Partners: LIBER, CESSDA/GESIS, CESSDA/UKDA, CLARIN/UL-FF, UCL), provided the curated content with input from the SSH Training Community. Task 6.3 Empowering Users: Training Materials and Online Learning Paths (Lead: DARIAH/OEAW; Partners: DARIAH ERIC, CLARIN ERIC, CLARIN/UL-FF, CESSDA/NSD, CESSDA/UKDA, UCL, CNR) developed, maintained, and updated the tool.

Training

Access the Training Discovery Toolkit

[Access the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit](#)

[SSHOSC Service Catalogue](#)

[in /company/sshoc](#)

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